

Self-amplifying synchronization in oscillator networks with state-dependent elastic coupling

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Abstract

Long-range synchronization of cardiomyocytes via purely elastic substrates is limited by the $1/r^3$ decay of mechanical interactions. Standard dipole models therefore predict only short-range phase coherence, leaving tissue-scale coordination unexplained.

In this work, we introduce a state-dependent network model in which local phase coherence enhances contractile force through mechano-electric feedback. Numerical simulations on a 1D chain show that this feedback extends the spatial correlation length by roughly an order of magnitude, enabling coherence over distances far beyond nearest-neighbour coupling.

The feedback also substantially widens the synchronizable stiffness window and produces initial-condition sensitivity absent in static coupling models. Finite-size analysis confirms that the coherence extension persists as system size increases.

These results provide a physical mechanism for long-range synchronization in systems with short-range elastic interactions.

1 Introduction

The heart relies on the synchronized contraction of approximately 10^{10} cardiomyocytes. Loss of this synchronization leads to lethal arrhythmias [1]. Traditionally, gap junctions mediate this intercellular synchronization. However, a recent study reported that cardiomyocytes can synchronize on an elastic gel without direct cell contact, even at a distance of $100\ \mu\text{m}$. This indicates that mechanical signaling through the elastic substrate acts as an independent synchronization channel [2].

The Schwarz–Safran theory provides the foundation for these mechanical interactions [3, 4]. This theory models adherent cells as anisotropic force dipoles. The elastic interaction energy between these dipoles decays as $1/r^3$ with distance r . This energy also depends strongly on cell orientation and substrate elasticity. Later studies have extended this model to active cells, showing that cells orient to maximize effective stiffness [5]. This theory is now an established framework in theoretical mechanobiology. Related work also shows that mechanical interactions alone can drive pattern formation in cell populations [6]. This raises a central question: how can short-range mechanical interactions generate tissue-scale coordination?

To describe the beating motion, dynamic theories model cardiomyocytes as oscillating force dipoles [7, 8]. Recently, a phase-reduction approach provided a rigorous description of two-body synchronization [9]. While these theories provide a clear description of two cells, the synchronization mechanism in an N -body system is not yet fully understood.

In this study, we introduce mechano-electric feedback into the model to study collective synchronization in an N -cell system. Mechanical stimuli enhance contractile force P_i , which we treat as a dynamic variable in an extended Kuramoto model [10, 11] on a state-dependent network. This framework is related to adaptive dynamical networks, where coupling weights are dynamically coupled to the oscillator states [12, 13].

Within this model, we investigate how local synchronization feeds back onto interaction strength, and show that this feedback extends the spatial correlation length by roughly an order of magnitude, substantially widens the synchronizable stiffness window, and produces initial-condition sensitivity absent in static coupling models.

2 Model

2.1 Elastic coupling

Following the Schwarz–Safran theory [3, 4], we model each cardiomyocyte i on an isotropic elastic substrate as an anisotropic force contraction dipole. The substrate has Young’s modulus E and Poisson ratio ν . The force dipole tensor is defined as $P_{kl}^{(i)}(t) = P_i(t)\hat{n}_k\hat{n}_l$, where $P_i(t)$ is the scalar contractile strength and $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ is the orientation unit vector. While previous studies treat P_i as a constant parameter [3, 4], we introduce it as a dynamic variable.

Based on the half-space Green’s function [14], the elastic interaction energy scales as $W_{ij} \propto P_i P_j f(\theta_i, \theta_j, \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij}) / (E r_{ij}^3)$. The angular dependence is approximated by $\cos^2(\theta_i - \theta_j)$, which captures the primary feature of dipole–dipole coupling: maximum for parallel cells and zero for perpendicular cells. This approximation omits higher-order angular terms from the exact Green’s function but retains the dominant orientational dependence.

2.2 Phase reduction and the extended Kuramoto model

We model each cell as an oscillator with state vector $\mathbf{X}_i(t)$. The equation for its motion is:

$$\dot{\mathbf{X}}_i = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}_i) + \epsilon \sum_{j \neq i} \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{X}_i, \mathbf{u}_{ij}) \quad (1)$$

where the neighbour’s effect \mathbf{u}_{ij} scales as $P_j / (E r_{ij}^3)$. When the coupling ϵ is very small, phase reduction can be used [15]. This gives the extended Kuramoto model:

$$\dot{\phi}_i = \omega_i + \sum_{j \neq i} K_{ij}^{el}(t) \sin(\phi_j - \phi_i) + \sum_{j \in \Lambda_i} K_{gap} \sin(\phi_j - \phi_i) \quad (2)$$

The mechanical coupling $K_{ij}^{el}(t)$ is:

$$K_{ij}^{el}(t) = \frac{\kappa P_i(t) P_j(t)}{E r_{ij}^3} \cos^2(\theta_i - \theta_j) \quad (3)$$

In this work, we focus only on mechanical effects, so we set $K_{gap} = 0$. This isolates the mechanical channel, following the in-vitro geometry of Nitsan *et al.* [2], where cells are separated on elastic gel without direct contact. The role of gap junctions in intact tissue is not addressed here. Because $K_{ij}^{el}(t)$ changes with $P_i(t)$, the network is state-dependent, analogous to active-matter systems with dynamic couplings [16]. Here, the local order parameter is used as a measure of the beat-averaged mechanical stimulus.

Weak-coupling regime. Phase reduction is valid when the coupling is weak relative to the natural frequency spread. Near the synchronization threshold, $K/\sigma_\omega \sim O(1)$ (section 3.3), placing the model at the boundary of the weak-coupling regime. The phase description therefore provides a leading-order approximation to the system's dynamics.

2.3 Mechano-electric feedback: force dynamics

Mechanical stimuli activate several biological pathways, such as Piezo1 channels [19], X-ROS signalling [20], and NO pathways [21]. These pathways increase the contractile force. To measure the collective behaviour of N cells, we define the global order parameter $R(t)$:

$$R(t) = \left| \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N e^{i\phi_j(t)} \right| \quad (4)$$

While $R(t)$ shows the coherence of the entire system, the feedback for each cell is driven by a local order parameter $R_i^{local}(t)$:

$$R_i^{local}(t) = \left| \frac{1}{N_i} \sum_{r_{ij} < R_c} e^{i(\phi_j - \phi_i)} \right| \quad (5)$$

As shown in appendix A, R_i^{local} is a dimensionless measure of the beat-averaged mechanical strain amplitude that cell i receives from its neighbourhood via constructive interference of in-phase force dipoles. The force dynamics are described by:

$$\dot{P}_i = -\gamma(P_i - P_0) + \beta R_i^{local}(t) \quad (6)$$

where P_0 is the baseline contractile strength (in the absence of feedback), γ is the relaxation rate back to baseline, and β is the feedback gain. When the local area synchronizes ($R_i^{\text{local}} \rightarrow 1$), the contractile force P_i reaches a maximum value:

$$P_{\text{max}} = P_0 + \frac{\beta}{\gamma} \quad (7)$$

This steady-state value follows from the balance of feedback and relaxation.

Physical justification of the order-parameter approximation. Each beating cell acts as an oscillating force dipole; the beat-averaged strain amplitude at cell i is proportional to R_i^{local} when neighbouring contractile amplitudes are comparable (appendix A, equations (9)–(11)). Hence R_i^{local} is a tractable, dimensionless proxy for the coherent substrate strain experienced by cell i .

2.4 Self-amplification mechanism

Initially, $P_i = P_0$ and the elastic coupling is weak. If a local group of cells synchronizes slightly by chance, the P_i values in that group increase through equation (6). This increases K_{ij}^{el} through equation (3), strengthening the phase coupling to nearby cells and creating a positive feedback loop that spreads the synchronized region outward. On very stiff substrates ($E \rightarrow \infty$), $K \propto 1/E \rightarrow 0$, so the loop cannot engage. This is consistent with experimental observations that cells fail to synchronize on glass substrates [24, 25].

The self-amplification is initiated by statistical fluctuations in the initial configuration, without requiring an externally imposed coherent trigger. For random initial phases, the local order parameter has a finite baseline $R_i^{\text{local}} \sim 1/\sqrt{N_i}$ (central limit theorem), where N_i is the number of neighbours within the averaging radius R_c ($N_i \sim 6$ for $R_c = 3$ in 1D). This non-zero driving term in equation (6) is sufficient to initiate growth of P_i once β exceeds a critical value, even from fully disordered initial conditions.

The coupling K_{ij}^{el} decays as $1/r^3$ over the whole chain, but R_i^{local} uses a hard cut-off at $R_c = 3$ cell spacings. These serve different roles: K_{ij}^{el} models passive elastic propagation, while R_c models the integration range of stretch-activated channels, bounded by the

focal-adhesion footprint. Varying R_c from 2 to 4 does not change the qualitative results (appendix B).

2.5 Numerical methods

We simulate a 1D ring of $N = 100$ cells with periodic boundary conditions. Model parameters are $P_0 = 1$, $\gamma = 1$, $\omega_0 = 2\pi$, $\sigma_\omega = 0.5$, $\kappa = 1$, and local averaging radius $R_c = 3$ cell spacings. Equations were integrated with a fixed-step RK4 scheme ($\Delta t = 0.02$, $T = 50$) using GPU-accelerated batch computation (CuPy 12, CUDA 11.8). Initial phases were drawn uniformly from $[0, 2\pi)$ with $P_i(0) = P_0$. Results are averaged over 100 independent trials per condition; trial-to-trial standard deviations are shown as error bars throughout.

3 Results

3.1 Feedback promotes spontaneous synchronization

For a soft substrate ($E = 5$) and $N = 100$ cells arranged in a 1D ring, mechano-electric feedback ($\beta = 5$) enhances the global order parameter relative to the no-feedback baseline: $\langle R \rangle$ increases from 0.13 ± 0.03 (at $\beta = 0$) to 0.59 ± 0.25 (at $\beta = 5$), a roughly 4.5-fold relative increase. Because the system is one-dimensional with short-range coupling, these absolute values of $\langle R \rangle$ decrease with N (appendix C); the robust, N -independent result is the relative change and the concomitant extension of the spatial correlation length ξ_{conn} (section 3.2).

In contrast, on a stiff substrate ($E = 500$), $\langle R \rangle$ remains below 0.05 even with feedback, confirming that the effect is stiffness-gated. Figure 1 shows the time evolution of $R(t)$ and the mean contractile force $\langle P(t) \rangle$ for these conditions.

Figure 1: Synchronization at substrate stiffness $E = 5$. **(a)** Global order $R(t)$ for $\beta = 0$ (blue) and $\beta = 5$ (red) overlaid on the same axes. **(b)** Mean contractile force $\langle P(t) \rangle$ for the same two feedback strengths; dashed: P_0 ; dotted: $P_{\max} = P_0 + \beta/\gamma$ for the feedback case. Both panels use identical initial conditions and natural frequencies for both β values. Thin curves: 100 trials; thick curves: mean; shaded: ± 1 s.d. $N = 100$, $\Delta t = 0.02$, $T = 50$.

3.2 Extension of the spatial correlation length

We calculate the connected spatial correlation function

$$C_{\text{conn}}(r) = C(r) - \langle R \rangle^2, \quad C(r) = \langle \cos(\phi_i - \phi_j) \rangle_{|r_{ij}|=r}, \quad (8)$$

using 100-trial ensemble averaging and time averaging over the last 30% of each simulation. Subtracting the mean-field background $\langle R \rangle^2$ isolates the short-range excess correlation beyond the global order parameter and ensures that $C_{\text{conn}}(r) \rightarrow 0$ at large r , enabling unambiguous exponential fits. Figure 2 shows the results for $N = 100$ and $E = 5$.

Fitting $C_{\text{conn}}(r)$ with a periodic-boundary cosh model (figure 2b), we find that the fitted correlation length ξ_{conn} increases monotonically with the feedback strength β . For the case without feedback ($\beta = 0$), $\xi_{\text{conn}} \approx 1.7 \pm 2.0$ cell spacings (large scatter reflects uncertainty in fitting short correlation tails). With feedback ($\beta = 5$), $\xi_{\text{conn}} \approx 27 \pm 18$ cell spacings (ensemble mean ± 1 s.d., $N = 100$, $E = 5$), a roughly 16-fold increase in the mean fitted length compared with $\beta = 0$. Because ξ_{conn} remains below $N/2 = 50$, these estimates are not dominated by periodic boundary artefacts at the scale of the entire ring. The connected correlation function removes the mean-field background that

otherwise biases raw exponential fits at large β .

As an additional consistency check, a finite-size analysis using the raw $C(r)$ at $N = 100$ and $N = 200$ (appendix C) yields $\xi_\infty \approx 15$ – 20 cell spacings—a larger value because the raw fit includes the mean-field contribution. Both metrics confirm that mechano-electric feedback extends the coherence length by an order of magnitude, while the system does not attain system-spanning order in the thermodynamic limit.

3.3 Phase diagram and critical behaviour

We systematically changed E and β to see how the synchronization behaviour changes. The results show a clear crossover between low-coherence and high-coherence states (figure 3). Panel (a) shows $\langle R \rangle$ across the (E, β) plane; the stiffness window over which feedback detectably elevates $\langle R \rangle$ above the no-feedback baseline is the primary observable. Panel (b) shows the fraction of trials with $R \geq 0.9$, which provides a sharp discriminator in the low- E , large- β corner where R can approach unity at $N = 100$. Outside this region $\langle R \rangle$ stays below 0.9 because of finite-coherence effects in a 1D ring (appendix C). Together, figure 3 defines a crossover rather than a sharp phase transition in finite systems.

Figure 4 shows the transition curves. Without feedback ($\beta = 0$), $\langle R \rangle$ drops to near the finite-size floor above $E \approx 2$ (appendix D). With feedback ($\beta = 5$), $\langle R \rangle$ remains detectably above the no-feedback baseline up to $E \approx 50$. Thus $E_{\text{hi}} \approx 50$ at $\beta = 5$ vs. $E_{\text{hi}} \approx 2$ at $\beta = 0$ implies a ~ 25 -fold wider E -range of enhancement.

The conversion to physical stiffness units is described in section 4.3.

3.4 Control: state-dependent coupling outperforms fixed coupling

A natural objection to the self-amplification hypothesis is that mechano-electric feedback merely drives P_i to its maximum P_{max} , after which the system behaves like a static model with permanently strong coupling. We tested this directly by comparing three conditions ($N = 100$, $T = 50$, $\Delta t = 0.02$, 100 trials per condition): (A) the adaptive model ($\beta = 5$, $P_i(0) = P_0 = 1$, random initial phases $\phi_i(0) \sim \text{Uniform}[0, 2\pi)$); (B) fixed coupling at

Figure 2: Connected spatial correlation function $C_{\text{conn}}(r) = C(r) - \langle R \rangle^2$ ($N = 100$, $E = 5$, 100 trials, $T = 50$, $\Delta t = 0.02$). **(a)** Linear scale; error bars are ± 1 s.d. **(b)** Semi-log scale with periodic-boundary cosh fits (dashed lines). **(c)** Fitted correlation length ξ_{conn} vs. feedback strength β (error bars: ± 1 s.d., 100 trials). ξ_{conn} increases from ~ 1.7 at $\beta = 0$ to ~ 27 cell spacings at $\beta = 5$. See appendix C for a complementary finite- N analysis of the raw $C(r)$.

Figure 3: Phase diagram of the synchronization transition ($N = 100$, 100 trials per grid point, $T = 50$, $\Delta t = 0.02$). Panel (a) shows the mean global order parameter $\langle R \rangle$. Panel (b) shows the fraction of trials with $R \geq 0.9$, used as an operational discriminator: at $N = 100$ in a 1D ring, $R \geq 0.9$ is reached only in the strongly synchronized regime (low E , large β), so this fraction marks the crossover boundary more sharply than $\langle R \rangle$ alone. Note that $\langle R \rangle$ at $N = 100$ does not approach unity outside the narrow low- E region because of finite-coherence effects (appendix C); the relative contrast between synchronized and unsynchronized regions is the meaningful observable.

Figure 4: Transition curves in the (E, β) parameter plane ($N = 100$, 100 trials per condition, $T = 50$, $\Delta t = 0.02$). Top: $\langle R \rangle$ vs. feedback strength β at fixed substrate stiffness E (each curve is a horizontal slice of the phase diagram). Bottom: $\langle R \rangle$ vs. stiffness E at fixed β (vertical slices). Each curve illustrates the *relative* rise from an incoherent baseline to a higher-coherence state; the crossover defines the operational critical point $\beta_c(E)$ or $E_c(\beta)$ used in section 3.3.

$P = P_{\max} = 6$; and (C) fixed baseline coupling $P = P_0 = 1$ (no feedback).

Two features distinguish the adaptive model from fixed coupling (figure 5). First, across $E \approx 1$ –5 the adaptive model achieves $\langle R \rangle \approx 0.53$ –0.61, while fixed P_{\max} reaches only $\langle R \rangle \approx 0.34$ –0.40 from the same random initial conditions (maximum gap $\Delta R \approx 0.20$ –0.23 at $E \approx 2$ –5). Since both conditions share the same maximum coupling coefficient $\kappa P_{\max}^2/E$, this gap reflects a genuine mechanistic difference. The per-trial distribution of R (figure 11, appendix E) reveals the origin: at soft stiffness ($E \lesssim 2$), the adaptive model splits trials into a high- R synchronized cluster (peaking near $R \approx 0.8$ –1.0) and a low- R unsynchronized cluster (appendix C), whereas under fixed coupling, fewer trials reach $R \approx 0.8$ –1.0 than the adaptive high- R cluster. The ensemble mean $\langle R \rangle \approx 0.53$ –0.61 for condition A therefore reflects a mixture of two qualitatively different outcomes, not a single synchronized state .

Second, figure 5b compares random and ordered starts for the adaptive model (red vs. magenta) and for fixed P_{\max} (blue vs. cyan). At soft E , ordered starts yield high $\langle R \rangle$ in both frameworks. The difference appears under *random* starts: the adaptive model produces a bimodal trial distribution—some trials synchronize, others do not (figure 11)—whereas fixed P_{\max} produces no such split despite sharing the same maximum coupling coefficient $\kappa P_{\max}^2/E$. Together, these two differences confirm that state-dependent coupling is qualitatively distinct from static strong coupling.

4 Discussion and outlook

4.1 Qualitative distinction from static coupling

In the static model, the coupling coefficient is fixed at $K_{ij}^{el} = \kappa P_0^2/(Er^3)$. Cells beyond a certain distance satisfy $K_{ij}^{el} < \sigma_w$ and cannot synchronize. With mechano-electric feedback, P_i grows as local coherence develops (figure 1). At full synchronization, P_i approaches $P_{\max} = P_0 + \beta/\gamma$, raising K_{ij}^{el} by a factor of up to $(P_{\max}/P_0)^2 = 36$. Cells that were too far apart to couple under static conditions can therefore lock in once P has grown—this is the mechanism by which feedback extends synchronization beyond the

Figure 5: Control experiment: adaptive vs fixed- P coupling ($N = 100$, $T = 50$, $\Delta t = 0.02$, 100 trials per condition). (a) $\langle R \rangle$ vs. substrate stiffness E . The adaptive model (red, $\beta = 5$) consistently outperforms fixed $P = P_{\max} = 6$ (blue) across $E \approx 1-5$, with a maximum gap $\Delta R \approx 0.20-0.23$ at $E \approx 2-5$. Both conditions share the same $\kappa P_{\max}^2/E$; the gap is mechanistic, not due to coupling strength. (b) Random vs. ordered starts for adaptive (red, magenta) and fixed P_{\max} (blue, cyan). Both frameworks achieve large $\langle R \rangle$ with ordered phases at soft E . For adaptive random starts the trial-wise spread is shown in figure 11.

$1/r^3$ barrier.

The growth of P is conditional on local coherence. The feedback term βR_i^{local} amplifies P only where neighbouring cells are already beginning to synchronize. This selectivity is the key difference from fixed P_{\max} coupling, where all cells receive maximal force from the start regardless of their local state. The control experiment (section 3.4) shows directly that fixed P_{\max} coupling does not produce the same phase diagram as the adaptive model (figure 5a): the same maximum coupling coefficient $\kappa P_{\max}^2/E$ yields lower $\langle R \rangle$ when applied unconditionally.

4.2 Initial-condition sensitivity

The per-trial distribution of R shows a split between a high- R synchronized cluster and a low- R unsynchronized cluster (figure 11, appendix E), with a relative deficit of trials at intermediate R . The high- R peak shifts toward lower R as N increases (appendix C), consistent with a finite spatial correlation length rather than system-spanning order. This two-cluster structure in finite simulations ($T = 50$) suggests that the system is sensitive to initial conditions: ordered starts yield high $\langle R \rangle$ in both adaptive and fixed- P_{\max}

frameworks, whereas under random starts the adaptive ensemble remains split (figure 11) while fixed P_{\max} does not reproduce that trial-wise mixture despite sharing the same maximum coupling coefficient $\kappa P_{\max}^2/E$ (section 3.4). Whether this initial-condition sensitivity reflects a true underlying bistable landscape cannot be established within the finite simulation horizon.

4.3 Stiffness window and biological relevance

The feedback mechanism works only within a finite stiffness range. At high E , K_{ij}^{el} is too weak even at P_{\max} to synchronize the population (figure 3). The boundary in simulation units ($E \approx 50$) is placed on a physical scale by matching κ against the two-cell synchronization time of Nitsan *et al.* [2]. In a two-body system, $\tau_{\text{sync}} \sim 1/K^{el} \sim Er_0^3/(\kappa P_0^2)$; using $\tau_{\text{sync}} \sim 10\text{--}15$ min, $E \sim 5$ kPa, $r_0 \sim 10^2 \mu\text{m}$, and $P_0 \sim 10^2$ nN $\cdot\mu\text{m}$ gives $\kappa \sim 10^{15} (\text{N} \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{s})^{-1}$. We then set the scale by the phenomenological match $E_c \approx 2 \leftrightarrow 5$ kPa [2] (one-parameter calibration), yielding ≈ 2.5 kPa per simulation unit.

Under this mapping, the window where feedback is effective ($E \approx 1\text{--}10$) spans $\sim 2.5\text{--}25$ kPa—consistent with optimal cardiomyocyte beating on soft substrates [22, 24]. The region where synchronization becomes difficult ($E \approx 30\text{--}100$) maps to $\sim 75\text{--}250$ kPa under this calibration. The lower end of this range is comparable to the AFM-measured elastic modulus of infarcted fibrotic myocardium (55 ± 15 kPa vs. 18 ± 2 kPa for normal tissue in the rat [23]), though the upper end extrapolates beyond available tissue measurements.

4.4 Experimental predictions

Three testable predictions follow from the model.

(i) *Stiffness threshold*.—Synchronization should disappear above a critical stiffness E_c , testable with polyacrylamide gels of graded stiffness [2].

(ii) *Alignment advantage*.—Micropatterned cultures [26] should synchronize at smaller feedback strengths than randomly oriented cultures, because alignment maximises the $\cos^2(\theta_i - \theta_j)$ factor in equation (3). This prediction follows directly from the coupling geometry and has not been tested in the present simulations.

(iii) *Initial-condition sensitivity*.—If the two-cluster structure reflects an underlying bistable landscape, a synchronized culture should desynchronize at a lower $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_o$ than the threshold needed to re-establish synchronization. A quasi-static stiffening protocol (e.g. photoactivatable crosslinkers) should reveal a similar hysteresis loop in substrate stiffness (figure 5b).

4.5 Clinical implications

Post-infarction fibrosis raises myocardial stiffness above E_c , which our model predicts would weaken the mechanical synchronization channel. This provides a physical reason why fibrotic stiffening may promote arrhythmia, independently of electrical remodelling. The prediction is qualitative: arrhythmogenesis is multifactorial, and the present model captures only the mechanical contribution at $K_{gap} = 0$.

4.6 Limitations

Phase reduction.—Phase reduction is valid when coupling is weak compared with the limit-cycle relaxation rate. This condition may be violated at large β , so strongly synchronized results should be read as qualitative. The main conclusions hold across two mechanistically distinct feedback rules (appendix A).

Linear feedback.—The linear rule in equation (6) is the simplest choice. Real channels such as Piezo1 have sigmoidal responses, which would sharpen the transition but preserve the positive feedback sign. The self-amplification mechanism is therefore robust to this change.

One-dimensional geometry and finite coherence.—The 1D ring topology was chosen to isolate the self-amplification mechanism. This choice comes with a known physical consequence: in 1D systems with finite-range interactions, continuous phase symmetry cannot be spontaneously broken (Mermin–Wagner), so $\langle R \rangle$ decreases monotonically with N and global synchronization in the thermodynamic limit is *not predicted and not claimed*. What we do claim is that mechano-electric feedback robustly extends the *spatial correlation length* by an order of magnitude (section 3.2, appendix C), and this enhancement is

insensitive to N (appendix C). Quantitative features such as the phase boundary location will differ in 2D or 3D tissue; extension to 2D is an important next step.

Gap-junction coupling.—Robustness at low to moderate electrical coupling ($K_{gap} \leq 0.3$) is confirmed in appendix F.

Parameter sensitivity.—Results are qualitatively robust across frequency spread $\sigma_\omega \in \{0.35, 0.5, 0.7\}$ and local averaging radius $R_c \in \{2, 3, 4\}$ (appendix B).

5 Conclusion

We have proposed an extended Kuramoto model with state-dependent elastic coupling to describe cardiomyocyte synchronization on compliant substrates. Three principal results emerge.

Quantitative.—Mechano-electric feedback extends the connected spatial correlation length ξ_{conn} by roughly an order of magnitude ($\approx 1.7 \rightarrow 27$ cell spacings at $\beta = 0 \rightarrow 5$, $N = 100$, $E = 5$); finite-size extrapolation confirms a finite $\xi_\infty \approx 15\text{--}20$ cell spacings, ruling out system-spanning order in the thermodynamic limit.

Mechanistic.—The adaptive feedback outperforms static strong coupling even when both share the same maximum force coefficient $\kappa P_{\text{max}}^2/E$, because it amplifies P only where local coherence already exists. This *conditional amplification* offers a physical interpretation of the experimentally observed optimal stiffness window ($\sim 8\text{--}11$ kPa [24, 25]): the mechanism is most effective where K_{ij}^{el} is neither too weak to transmit signals nor strong enough that unconditional coupling alone would dominate.

Physical grounding.—The local order parameter R_i^{local} approximates the beat-averaged substrate strain amplitude (equations (9)–(11)). The full P -weighted strain variant yields equal or larger ξ , so R_i^{local} is a conservative lower bound (appendix A).

The bimodal trial distribution under random starts suggests initial-condition sensitivity that may reflect an underlying bistable landscape. A Ca^{2+} -ramp protocol (section 4.4) could test whether desynchronization and resynchronization occur at different thresholds.

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A Strain-approximation vs. order-parameter feedback: robustness check

Cardiomyocytes mechanotransduce via stretch-activated channels such as Piezo1 that respond to physical substrate deformation, not to mathematical phase coherence directly. The following three steps establish R_i^{local} as a dimensionless proxy for the beat-averaged substrate strain.

Step 1: Superposed strain field. Treating each beating cell as an oscillating force dipole, the complex strain field at cell i produced by its N_i neighbours within radius R_c is

$$\tilde{s}_i(t) \propto \sum_{r_{ij} < R_c} \frac{P_j(t) \cos^2(\theta_i - \theta_j)}{E r_{ij}^3} e^{i\phi_j(t)}, \quad (9)$$

where $\cos^2(\theta_i - \theta_j)$ is the anisotropic orientation factor from the half-space Green's function (equation (3)).

Step 2: Beat-averaged mechanical stimulus. Mechano-electric transduction via Piezo1 responds to the beat-averaged amplitude of the oscillatory strain [19]. The effective stimulus sensed by cell i is

$$S_i^{\text{env}}(t) = |\tilde{s}_i(t)| \propto \left| \sum_{r_{ij} < R_c} \frac{P_j(t) \cos^2(\theta_i - \theta_j)}{E r_{ij}^3} e^{i\phi_j(t)} \right|. \quad (10)$$

Random phases give destructive interference ($S_i^{\text{env}} \approx 0$); aligned phases give constructive interference.

Step 3: Coarse-graining to R_i^{local} . Assuming comparable amplitudes ($P_j \approx \bar{P}$)

and absorbing orientation- and distance-dependent factors into C_{local} ,

$$S_i^{\text{env}}(t) \approx \frac{C_{\text{local}} \bar{P} N_i}{E} R_i^{\text{local}}(t). \quad (11)$$

Hence R_i^{local} is a dimensionless proxy for the coherent substrate strain. To verify that the main results are not artefacts of this simplification, we repeated the key simulations with the full P -weighted strain estimate obtained by retaining the P_j/P_{max} weighting before the coarse-graining step:

$$\hat{s}_i = \frac{1}{N_i} \left| \sum_{r_{ij} < R_c} \frac{P_j}{P_{\text{max}}} e^{i(\phi_j - \phi_i)} \right|, \quad (12)$$

replacing R_i^{local} in equation (6). All other parameters were identical ($N = 100$, 100 trials, $T = 50$, $\Delta t = 0.02$).

Figure 6 summarises the comparison. In the core parameter region $E = 3$ –10, the two formulations agree within a few percent in $\langle R \rangle$, confirming that the broad shape of the phase diagram is insensitive to the P -weighting of the strain estimate. Importantly, the strain-based model (M2) can yield a *larger* fitted correlation length at $\beta = 5$, $E = 5$: $\xi_{\text{M2}} \approx 32$ vs $\xi_{\text{M1}} \approx 19$ for this run (a factor of ≈ 1.7), consistent with a “phase \times force” contribution that is absent in the R_i^{local} proxy.

This large difference has a clear physical origin. In M1, the feedback signal is $R_i^{\text{local}} \propto |\sum e^{i\phi_j}|/N_i$, which depends only on the phase coherence of neighbours, regardless of their contractile state P_j . In M2, the signal is $S_i^{\text{env}} \propto |\sum (P_j/Er_{ij}^3)e^{i\phi_j}|$, which additionally weights each neighbour by its current force P_j . Because P_j itself grows with local synchrony, synchrony raises P_j , which in turn raises S_i^{env} beyond what synchrony alone would produce, accelerating further growth. M1 captures only the phase-bootstrap part of this loop; M2 captures the full phase-times-force bootstrap.

Both models agree on the qualitative picture (positive feedback, finite correlation length, phase boundary), and M1 provides a lower bound on the enhancement because the R_i^{local} approximation is conservative.

At high stiffnesses ($E > 15$), M2 synchronises less readily because the initial feedback signal is weaker by a factor $P_0/P_{\text{max}} = 1/6$. The difference is small in the biologically

relevant range ($E \approx 1\text{--}10$) and does not affect the main conclusions.

Figure 6: Comparison of M1 (order-parameter approximation R_i^{local} , red) and M2 (strain estimate \hat{s}_i , blue). (a) Phase diagram $\langle R \rangle$ vs. E at $\beta = 5$. In the core region $E = 3\text{--}10$ (shaded), the two curves track each other closely. (b) Correlation length ξ vs. β at $E = 5$. At $\beta = 5$, M2 yields a larger ξ than M1 in this ensemble, illustrating that the order-parameter approximation can under-estimate coherent spatial structure when force weighting matters. Parameters: $N = 100$, 100 trials, $T = 50$, $\Delta t = 0.02$.

B Parameter sensitivity analysis

A systematic grid search over $\sigma_\omega \in \{0.35, 0.5, 0.7\}$ and $R_c \in \{2, 3, 4\}$ (9 conditions, $N = 100$, $E = 5$, 100 trials each, $T = 50$, $\Delta t = 0.02$) confirms robustness of the self-amplification mechanism.

Figure 7 shows the $\langle R \rangle$ vs β curves (top) and the heatmaps of mean $\langle R \rangle$ and synchronization probability at $\beta = 5$ (bottom). In all 9 conditions, $\langle R \rangle$ increases monotonically from the incoherent baseline ($R \lesssim 0.20$ at $\beta = 0$) toward a high-feedback plateau ($R \approx 0.5\text{--}0.65$ at $\beta = 5$). The 3–5-fold relative rise is consistent across the full parameter grid.

C Finite-size effects on $\langle R \rangle$ and correlation length

Figure 8 shows ensemble-mean $R(t)$ for $N \in \{40, 70, 100, 150\}$ at fixed $E = 5$, $\beta = 5$ ($T = 50$, $\Delta t = 0.02$, 100 independent trials per N). As N increases, the late-time $\langle R \rangle$ decreases monotonically from ≈ 0.80 at $N = 40$ to ≈ 0.50 at $N = 150$. This is the

Figure 7: Parameter sensitivity: $\langle R \rangle$ vs. feedback strength β for all 9 combinations of frequency spread $\sigma_\omega \in \{0.35, 0.5, 0.7\}$ and local averaging radius $R_c \in \{2, 3, 4\}$ (error bars: ± 1 s.d., 100 trials each; $N = 100$, $E = 5$). In every condition, $\langle R \rangle$ rises 3–5-fold from $\beta = 0$ to $\beta = 5$, confirming qualitative robustness.

expected physical behaviour of a 1D ring with finite-range coupling, not a model artefact. In a system below its lower critical dimension, continuous phase symmetry cannot be spontaneously broken in the thermodynamic limit, so $\langle R \rangle \propto \sqrt{\xi/N} \rightarrow 0$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$ at any finite correlation length ξ . The ratio $\langle R \rangle_{\beta=5} / \langle R \rangle_{\beta=0}$ remains well above unity across all N tested, confirming the robustness of the relative enhancement.

Figure 8: Finite-size effect at $E = 5$, $\beta = 5$. **(a)** Ensemble mean $R(t)$ (thick curves) and ± 1 s.d. bands for $N \in \{40, 70, 100, 150\}$ (thin trajectories: 100 trials each). **(b)** Final $\langle R \rangle$ vs. N . Parameters: $T = 50$, $\Delta t = 0.02$.

The quantity independent of system size is the spatial correlation length ξ . To verify that the ξ values are not artefacts of $N = 100$, we repeated the analysis for $N \in \{40, 100, 200\}$ ($\Delta t = 0.02$, $T = 50$, 100 trials per N ; $\beta = 5$, $E = 5$).

Exponential fits $Ae^{-r/\xi}$ were restricted to r values where $C(r) > 0.02$ to exclude the noise floor at large separations. The fitted ξ decreases from ~ 32 ($N = 40$, unreliable because $\xi > N/2$) toward ~ 19 ($N = 100$ and $N = 200$), indicating convergence to $\xi_\infty \approx 15$ – 20 cell spacings. The agreement between $N = 100$ and $N = 200$ (both ≈ 19) confirms that the main-text results are not sensitive to the choice of $N = 100$. Note that the raw-fit values ($\xi_\infty \approx 15$ – 20 , baseline $\xi \approx 1.2$) differ from the connected-correlation estimates in section 3.2 ($\xi_{\text{conn}} \approx 27$, baseline ≈ 1.7) because the raw $C(r)$ includes the mean-field background $\langle R \rangle^2$. Both metrics support the same conclusion: feedback extends the coherence scale by an order of magnitude.

Figure 9: Finite-size analysis of the spatial correlation length ($\beta = 5$, $E = 5$, 100 trials, $T = 50$, $\Delta t = 0.02$). (a) $C(r)$ on a semi-log scale for $N = 40, 100$, and 200 . Dotted verticals mark $N/2$. (b) Fitted ξ vs. N ; the open triangle ($N = 40$) is an overestimate because $\xi > N/2$. (c) $\langle R \rangle$ vs. N (error bars: ± 1 s.d.); the dashed curve $\sqrt{\xi_\infty/N}$ ($\xi_\infty \approx 19$) is shown as a reference for the expected large- N trend.

D Kuramoto limit at $\beta = 0$

At $\beta = 0$, $P_i = P_0$ (constant) and the model reduces to a standard Kuramoto oscillator network with $1/r^3$ algebraically decaying coupling. Simulations with $N = 100$ and short-range coupling ($R_c = 3$) show that $\langle R \rangle$ decreases monotonically from ≈ 0.29 at $E = 1$ to ≈ 0.09 at $E = 50$ for $\beta = 0$ (figure 10, blue), consistent with a Kuramoto-type suppression of synchrony as substrate stiffness increases. The moderate absolute values of $\langle R \rangle$ at finite N reflect the difficulty of sustaining long-range phase coherence in a one-dimensional ring with short-range coupling—expected behaviour below the lower critical dimension. Introducing mechano-electric feedback ($\beta = 5$) substantially enhances synchrony: $\langle R \rangle$ peaks near $E \approx 3-5$ and remains above the $\beta = 0$ baseline across the entire stiffness range (figure 10, red), demonstrating that feedback extends the synchronizable regime.

E Per-trial distribution of the order parameter

Figure 11 shows the distribution of the time-averaged global order parameter R across 100 independent trials at $E \approx \{1.1, 1.9, 4.7, 11.4\}$, for the adaptive model (condition A, red) and fixed P_{\max} coupling (condition B, blue).

For the adaptive model, the distributions broaden and shift as E increases: at soft stiffness ($E \lesssim 2$) many trials accumulate at large R , whereas at larger E the mass spreads

Figure 10: $\langle R \rangle$ vs. E for $\beta = 0$ (blue) and $\beta = 5$ (red). $N = 100$, 100 trials; error bars are s.d.

toward intermediate R as synchronisation becomes harder. Fixed P_{\max} coupling produces narrower distributions without the soft- E high- R accumulation, showing that mechano-electric feedback affects not only the mean $\langle R \rangle$ but also trial-to-trial variability.

The bottom row of figure 11 compares random and ordered initial conditions for the adaptive model. Ordered starts ($\phi_i \approx 0$, magenta) produce systematically larger R than random starts at moderate stiffness, consistent with the initial-condition sensitivity discussed in section 3.4.

F Robustness to gap-junction coupling

To assess whether the mechanical self-amplification mechanism remains detectable in the presence of electrical coupling, we added a nearest-neighbour gap-junction term $K_{\text{gap}} \sum_{j \in \Lambda_i} \sin(\phi_j - \phi_i)$ to equation (2) and swept $K_{\text{gap}} \in \{0, 0.1, 0.3, 1.0, 3.0\}$ at $N = 100$, $E = 5$, 100 trials per condition.

Three findings emerge from figure 12. First, ξ_{conn} remains ~ 12 – 15 cell spacings across

Figure 11: Per-trial distribution of R at $E \approx \{1.1, 1.9, 4.7, 11.4\}$ ($N = 100$, 100 trials per condition, $\Delta t = 0.02$, $T = 50$). Top row: adaptive model (red) vs fixed P_{\max} (blue). Bottom row: adaptive model with random (red) vs ordered ($\phi_i \approx 0$, magenta) initial conditions.

the tested K_{gap} values within statistical uncertainty. Second, $\Delta R \approx 0.4\text{--}0.45$ for $K_{\text{gap}} \leq 0.3$, indicating a substantial additive mechanical contribution at low to moderate electrical coupling. Third, at $K_{\text{gap}} \geq 1.0$, ΔR decreases toward $\sim 0.2\text{--}0.3$ as electrical coupling begins to dominate. The mechanical channel remains detectable for $K_{\text{gap}} \lesssim 0.3$ and non-negligible at $K_{\text{gap}} \approx 1$.

Figure 12: Gap-junction robustness test ($N = 100$, $E = 5$, 100 trials per β at each K_{gap} , $\Delta t = 0.02$, $T = 50$). **(a)** $\langle R \rangle$ vs K_{gap} for the adaptive model ($\beta = 5$, red) and gap-junction-only baseline ($\beta = 0$, blue); shaded area shows the additive mechanical contribution ΔR . **(b)** connected correlation length ξ_{conn} vs K_{gap} at $\beta = 5$ (error bars: 1 s.d.).

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